

MRI dataset for susceptibility-based radiomic feature extraction

About Us

The Institute of Neurological Sciences of Bologna (ISNB) is a Scientific Institute for Hospitalization and Care (IRCCS) recognized by the Ministry of Health in 2011. Like all IRCCS, the Institute of Neurological Sciences is a hospital of excellence that pursues research purposes, mainly clinical and translational, ultimately aimed at developing new therapeutic solutions.

The Functional and Molecular Neuroimaging Program (director Prof. Caterina Tonon) carries out conventional MRI and CT diagnostic activities integrated with the most advanced functional methods for the study of central nervous and neuromuscular systems pathology, aimed at patients in inpatient, outpatient and day hospital settings.

Our activity is backed by a multidisciplinary team, with expertise in different fields - neurology, neuroradiology, neurosurgery, neuropsychology, bioengineering, physics, neuropathology and clinical molecular biology - and makes use of a Neuroimaging Laboratory, established in collaboration with the University of Bologna, which supports the development and quantitative analysis of structural and functional sequences.

The dataset

Included within the database acquired at the ISNB are anonymized and de-identified brain images from 150 individuals, as part of a study approved by the local ethics review board.

Specifically, the database includes multiparametric MRI brain images (anatomical T₁w and T₂w, DWI and QSM) within a mixed sample of 100 patients with multiple sclerosis and 50 healthy controls. We focused on the normal appearing white matter and some of its tracts (arcuate fasciculus, cortico-spinal tract, frontal aslant tract, inferior fronto-occipital fasciculus, optic radiation, uncinata fasciculus), from which we extracted susceptibility-based radiomic features, also provided in the database. Data are organized according to the Brain Imaging Directory Structure (BIDS)

More details about image acquisition and processing may be found in Fiscone et al. Multiparametric MRI dataset for susceptibility-based radiomic feature extraction and analysis, Scientific Data (2024).

Use of this dataset

The dataset is made accessible in accordance with FAIR Principles. Metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. An investigator who wishes to access the dataset for the purposes of research or education should apply for authorization, which will be granted upon receipt of a completed Data Use Agreement (DUA). Under the DUA, the named investigator agrees to abide by policies for safeguarding the privacy of participants who contributed to the dataset, and for eventual publication and citation.

Access to the dataset

To obtain the access to the dataset, the following steps must be completed:

1. Create an account on [Zenodo](#), the open repository, ensuring that either the username or the email address (or both) are public. If you already have a Zenodo account, make sure that at least one of these identifiers is public.
2. Complete and sign the Data Use Agreement below, and send a PDF of the signed copy to radiomicsdataset@live.unibo.it. You should put the words 'Request access' in the subject line, and in the body of the text communicate the identifying information you made public when you activated your Zenodo account, i.e. username or email address.
3. Within two working days, you will be granted the 'Reader' access to the community 'MRI_dataset_susceptibility-based_radiomic_features'. You can check the requests directly on Zenodo ('My dashboard > Requests'). You should also receive a notification via email. Please check the 'Other' or 'Spam' folders if you do not see it.
4. Accept the request to join the Zenodo community, and you will have access to the dataset and download the data.

MRI dataset for susceptibility-based radiomic feature extraction:

Data Use Agreement

I request access to the 'MRI dataset for susceptibility-based radiomic feature extraction', provided by the Functional and Molecular Neuroimaging Unit, IRCCS *Istituto delle Scienze Neurologiche di Bologna*, Italy, and stored on the Zenodo repository.

By accepting this agreement, I agree to access the data under the following terms:

1. Under the terms of the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) I am the data controller of the data that I access.
2. I will refrain from trying to determine the identity of the study participants. I will avoid associating this data with any other database in a manner that could disclose identifying information. I will not request the pseudonymization key connecting this data to an individual's personal information, and I will not obtain any additional details about individual participants.
3. I will not attempt to contact the study participants.
4. I will not redistribute these data or share access to these data with others, including individuals in my institution and my colleagues working elsewhere.
5. I commit to adhering to all pertinent rules and regulations established by both my institution and the government. This agreement does not take precedence over the prevailing general data protection regulations already in effect in my country.
6. I will reference the specific source of the accessed data when publicly presenting any results or algorithms that benefited from their use: (a) reports in learned journals, magazine articles, book chapters, books, posters, oral presentations, and all other presentations of results derived from the data should acknowledge the origin of the data as follows: "Data were provided by the Functional and Molecular Neuroimaging Program, IRCCS *Istituto delle Scienze Neurologiche di Bologna*" ; (b) Authors of publications or presentations using the data should cite the article Fiscone et al., 'Multiparametric MRI dataset for susceptibility-based radiomic feature extraction and analysis', describing the methods developed and used to acquire and process the data; (c) The researchers who provide this data will not be included as authors of publications or presentations without their consent, and will not be held liable for any results and/or derived data.
7. I understand that if I do not abide by these terms then the agreement is no longer effective and I undertake to remove the data I obtained from any device or archive on which they have been stored.

Name:
Organization:
Email:

Place and date:

Signature: